

Agricultural Trade Regulation from France: The Role of EIGs

Problem encountered and objective

In France, Economic Interest Groups (EIGs) are strategic levers for agricultural producers who want to cooperate without losing their autonomy. They facilitate market access, reduce transaction costs, and strengthen bargaining power, while enabling the sharing of innovations and joint investments (certifications, equipment, digital tools).

Main results / outcomes

For small and medium-sized farms, joining or creating an EIG offers major benefits: increased competitiveness, risk pooling, and reduced administrative burdens, while maintaining the legal independence of each member.

Example: the Chapeau de Paille EIG brings together 35 pick-your-own farms covering 550 hectares and welcomes 2 million visitors per year. This model has reduced logistics costs, improved commercial visibility, and created a central purchasing unit to optimize supplies.

In a competitive agricultural context, economic interest groups are powerful and low-risk tools for strengthening resilience and supporting the agroecological transition, focusing on cooperation rather than concentration.

Thorigné harvest - Source: GIE Chapeau de Paille

Practical recommendations

From a legal standpoint, creating an EIG involves drafting a contract specifying the name, purpose, registered office, duration, information about the members, and the appointment of directors and their powers. No share capital is required, but at least two members must be engaged in an activity related to the purpose of the group.

Further information

[Chapeau de Paille: le site officiel du réseau des fermes Chapeau de Paille.](#)

About this abstract

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The EU4Advice project seeks to strengthen advisory services for Short Food Supply Chains (SFSC) actors, helping them adopt practices that are economically, socially, and environmentally sustainable. It connects SFSC advisors across all 27 Member States through a shared network and integrates SFSC-related tools and content into national Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS).